

Kinetics and inhibitory action of hydrolysis of *o*-nitrophenyl- β -D-galactopyranoside catalyzed by immobilized β -D-galactosidase on macroporous resin

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β -Galactosidase (β -D-galactoside galactosyl hydrolase EC 3.2.1.23) purified from *Cicer arietinum* has been immobilized on modified and activated macroporous resin D₂₀₂ (dimethylethoxymethylaminopolyphenylethylene anion-exchange resin) with high enzyme activity and high activity yield by means of adsorption of ions and crosslinked reaction. Catalytic kinetic results of immobilized β -galactosidase show that enzyme activity attains its maximum at 55°, pH 6.0, and the operational pH range and its thermostability range are increased compared to those of free enzyme. In addition, kinetic parameters K_m , V_m and E_a of the immobilized enzyme are slightly different from those of free enzyme. Raffinose, lactose and D-galactose are all reversible inhibitors for this enzyme. Their inhibitory kinetics are also studied.

β -Galactosidase shows good applied prospects in the dairy industry, and it is primarily used for the hydrolysis of lactose in milk and whey^{1,2}. The earlier studies were focussed on bacteria, fungus and yeast though β -galactosidase could be obtained plentifully from plants especially in various kinds of beans^{3,4}. The use of plant β -galactosidase might lower the high cost for lactose hydrolysis in milk products. In the present study, in a convenient way, β -galactosidase was obtained in high activity from *Cicer arietinum*, an abundant product in the northwest of China.

Recently, Axelsson and Zacchi⁵ reported that despite the high cost for enzyme attachment, immobilized β -galactosidase systems remain economically feasible compared to free enzyme systems. β -Galactosidase has been immobilized on cellulose derivatives⁶, polyacrylamide gel⁷ and porous glass³. However, with many of these supports, immobilization resulted in considerable reduction in enzyme activity as well as in binding capacity. In this paper, β -galactosidase was immobilized on modified macroporous resin D₂₀₂ with high binding capacity, retaining most of its enzyme activity. The catalytic kinetics and inhibitory kinetics of immobilized β -galactosidase have also been studied.

Results and Discussion

Immobilized enzyme : The extent of retention of enzyme after immobilization is an important factor for a suitable matrix. We obtained immobilized β -galactosidase with 63% retention of enzyme activity and also with relatively high activity (60 units/g dry resin). The retention of enzyme activity was compared with other immobilization methods. Okos *et al.*⁸ reported that only 6.29% retention of activity is obtained by physical adsorption method. Meng and Glatz⁹ have recently reported that approximately 50%

of the soluble enzyme activity is retained by membrane reactor method. The above comparison indicates that the modified D₂₀₂ is good support for plant β -galactosidase.

Optimum temperature and thermostability : The activities of free and immobilized β -galactosidase were measured at various temperature (40–70°) using ONPG (*o*-nitrophenyl- β -D-galactopyranoside) as substrate in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.0). The results show that optimum temperature of immobilized enzyme is the same as that of free enzyme (55°). In the range 40–70°, the free and immobilized enzymes were incubated for a long duration and the enzyme activity was determined in standard assay condition. The immobilized enzyme was found to be deactivated at a much slower rate than free enzyme. The activity of soluble enzyme decreased to 25% at 70° for 20 min, and almost to zero activity for 60 min at the same temperature. Immobilized β -galactosidase retained 72% activity at 70° for 20 min and 53% activity for 60 min. It can be concluded that immobilized β -galactosidase has better thermostability than free enzyme. The action between glutaraldehyde and amino group of β -galactosidase improves thermostability of immobilized β -galactosidase.

Optimum pH and pH stability : The activity of free β -galactosidase has optimum pH at 4.5, while that of immobilized β -galactosidase at pH 6.0. Free enzyme and immobilized enzyme were incubated at pH 2.0–14.0, 4° for 30 min, and the residual activity was measured under standard assay condition. The immobilized enzyme activity had wider pH range (6.0–12.0) than that of free enzyme (4.5–7.5) and a high retention of activity of almost 100%.

Kinetic parameters : At different temperatures, making Lineweaver-Burk plots of $1/v$ vs $1/[s]$ (Fig. 1) and $\log K_m$ vs $1/T$, we obtained the values of K_m , V_m and E_a . Table 1

shows that K_m and V_m values of immobilized β -galactosidase are slightly lower than that of free enzyme, which indicates that binding force of immobilized β -galactosidase and the substrate (ONPG) is increased. Also, E_a of immobilized enzyme has a difference of 18 kJ mol⁻¹ with that of free enzyme.

Fig. 1. Lineweave-Burk plots for immobilized β -galactosidase at pH 6.0 and at (O) 50°, (●) 55° and (⊙) 60°.

Table 1. Values of K_m , V_m and E_a for catalytic hydrolysis of ONPG by β -galactosidase at different temperatures

Parameter	Immobilized enzyme			Free enzyme	
	50°	55°	60°	40°	50°
K_m (mmol dm ⁻³)	9.1	11.8	25.0	10.8	57.9
V_m (μ mol min ⁻¹)	8.4	12.9	18.6	20.0	33.3
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)		90			72

Fig. 2. Lineweave-Burk plots for immobilized β -galactosidase in the presence of inhibitors: (a) lactose, (b) D-galactose and (c) raffinose. Concentration of inhibitors: (●) 10, (*) 20, (⊙) 40 mmol dm⁻³.

Effect of some compounds and buffers on the activity of immobilized β -galactosidase: The activity of immobilized β -galactosidase was determined with added buffer solutions, some organic and inorganic solutions under the optimum condition. Table 2 shows that buffer solutions and several organic solvents have negligible effect on the activity of immobilized β -galactosidase while metal ions and some organic solvents have considerable effect. Results here are different with those of free β -galactosidase. Improvements of metal ions (K^+ and Mg^{2+}) and organic solvents (CH_3CH_2OH , CH_2Cl_2 and $CHCl_3$) on immobilized β -galactosidase are larger than on free enzyme. It can be concluded that immobilization of β -galactosidase perhaps changes the environment of enzyme.

Table 2. Effect of buffer solutions, organic solvents and metal ions on the activity of immobilized β -galactosidase

Addition	Concentration	Relative activity (%)*
PBS	0.01 mol dm ⁻³ (pH 6.4)	100 (97)
Na ₂ HPO ₄ -Citrate	0.01 mol dm ⁻³ (pH 6.5)	94 (94)
Citric acid	0.1 mol dm ⁻³	89 (100)
Acetone	10%	94 (-)
Formaldehyde	10%	89 (-)
Methanol	10%	94 (75)
Ethanol	10%	110 (30)
Trichloromethane	10%	142 (-)
Dichloromethane	10%	120 (-)
KCl	10 mol dm ⁻³	116 (91.6)
	20 mol dm ⁻³	126 (96.5)
	40 mol dm ⁻³	147 (98.8)
MgCl ₂	5 mol dm ⁻³	100 (100)
	10 mol dm ⁻³	137 (104)
	20 mol dm ⁻³	142 (113)

*Value in parenthesis is the result of free β -galactosidase; (-) indicates, not measured.

Substrate inhibition: The inhibitory action of lactose, D-galactose and raffinose on immobilized β -galactosidase was studied. They were found to be reversible inhibitors which indicates that the balance between enzyme and inhibitors is obtained quickly. From Lineweave-Burk plots of inhibitory (Fig. 2), it may be concluded that lactose and D-galactose are competitive inhibitors while raffinose is non-competitive inhibitor. In competitive inhibition, the complex of enzyme-inhibitor (EI) and enzyme-substrate (ES) are formed. So, to obtain the same amount of ES in the condition of the same amount of enzyme, the amount of substrate should increase. In this case, V_m is retained while K_i (instead of K_m) is increased. In noncompetitive inhibition, the complex of enzyme-substrate-inhibitor (ESI) is formed. In this condition, K_m is retained while V_m is decreased. From Fig. 2, inhibitory constants (K_i) were evaluated lactose, 21.0; D-galactose, 16.2; raffinose, 28.9 mmol dm⁻³. The sequence of inhibition is D-galactose > lactose > raffinose.

Experimental

DEAE-cellulose (Pharmacia), ONPG (Sigma) and D₂₀₂ (China, Xi'an) were used. Lactose, D-galactose and raffinose and *Cicer arietinum* were local products. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Purification of β -galactosidase : All the steps of extraction and purification were carried out at 4° unless specified otherwise. Purification followed the process of crude extract, 30–70% ammonium sulfate fraction precipitation and DEAE-cellulose chromatography successively¹⁰. As three different protein peaks of β -galactosidase appeared in the eluted fraction of DEAE-cellulose, the first peak was collected as the material of immobilization.

Preparation of the supporter : D₂₀₂ was swollen with 70% ethanol, NaOH (1 mol dm⁻³), (NH₄)₂SO₄ (0.5 mol dm⁻³), HCl (2 mol dm⁻³) and phosphate buffer solution (pH 8.0; 0.01 mol dm⁻³) successively for 10–20 min, then washed with distilled water and stored at the room temperature.

Immobilization of β -galactosidase : D₂₀₂ was reacted with 21% glutaraldehyde solution at 4° for 12 h, then washed with distilled water and allowed to react with β -galactosidase in phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) at 4° for 10 h. The product (immobilized β -galactosidase) was filtered, washed with distilled water and stored at 4°.

Enzyme assay : The incubation mixture consisted of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ phosphate buffer solution (PBS; pH 6.0 (0.2 ml), 5 mmol dm⁻³ ONPG (0.2 ml) and enzyme (0.1 ml) (or 0.1

g immobilized enzyme). The incubation was carried out at 55° for 20 min, and ended with 1 mol dm⁻³ Na₂CO₃ (1.5 ml). The resulting reactive mixture was studied spectrophotometrically at 405 nm. The unit of enzyme was defined as the amount of enzyme that releases 0.1 μ mol of *o*-nitrophenyl (ONP) per min at 55°.

The reaction was carried out in the same condition above only with inhibitor (lactose, D-galactose, raffinose) instead of ONPG.

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References

1. A. Dahlqvist, B. Mattiasson and K. Mosbach, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.*, 1973, **15**, 395.
2. J. H. Woychik and M. V. Wondolowski, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1972, **289**, 347.
3. K. Golden, M. John and E. Kean, *Phytochemistry*, 1992, **34**, 355.
4. G. Simos, T. Giahnakouros and J. G. Georgatsos, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 2587.
5. A. Axelsson and G. Zacchi, *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.*, 1990, **24/25**, 678.
6. G. Kay and F. M. Groom, *Nature*, 1967, **216**, 514.
7. P. S. Buting and K. J. Laidler, *Biochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 4477.
8. M. R. Okos, A. Grakle and A. Syverson, *J. Food Sci.*, 1978, **43**, 566.
9. M. H. Meng and C. E. Glatz, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.*, 1994, **44**, 745.
10. X. Y. Li, K. H. Zhao, Y. F. Men and W. X. Tu, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1996, **105**, 217.